

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Ntadinobi****FIRST NAME: Chidozie Theophilus****PROGRAM CODE: DIRD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4 %

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. After your experience with the EUCLID Coursepack period one (1), which contains writing an academic essay, what may be the aim of an academic essay?¹

- To evaluate differing arguments - explain why one argument is more convincing than another.
- To produce your first academic research according to the orientation of the Euclid University guidelines.
- Academic essays seek to provide answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.**
- To express the fruit of your intellectual research to your readers.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack (Period 1)*, (Washington, D.C: Euclid Univ. Press, 2024), 7.

2. What is Plagiarism in academic writing?²
- It is taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet.
 - Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author for that source of information.**
 - Plagiarism is one of the academic tools to help students write quality essays.
 - Plagiarism is a method of citing the source of your argument and showing evidence of your claim.
3. According to the Turabian Rule of Style, underline the correct 'notes-bibliography footnote' for a book among the following citations:³
- Susanne Y. P. Choi and Yinni Peng, *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family, and Gender in China* (Oakland: University of California Press, 2016), 111–12 (Turabian 2018, 150).**
 - Choi, Susanne Y. P., and Yinni Peng. *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family, and Gender in China*. (Oakland: University of California Press), 2016.
 - Booth, Wayne C., Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *The Draft Research*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995.
 - French, R. M., trans. *The Way of a Pilgrim and The Pilgrim Continues His Way*. (New York: Ballantine Books-Random House), 1974.

² Ibid., 34.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 150.

4. What is the limitation of the study section in academic research and what is its aim?⁴
- It is a section in the dissertation research that uses the knowledge gained from the findings or the method to guide future research. Doctoral students or other researchers can use this knowledge to design studies that further narrow gaps in literature.
 - It is a section that provides a series of recommendations that are based on the knowledge gained from the dissertation research. These help then advance theory, research, practice, education, and training.
 - A section that presents anticipation of constraints in a dissertation paper.
 - This section explains the unexpected circumstances that constrain the interpretation of the dissertation research findings. It helps the reader judge whether the method used in the dissertation research provided an appropriate opportunity to answer the research questions.**
5. In a Dissertation, what element is used to answer the research questions or test the hypotheses derived from the research questions?⁵
- Qualitative and Quantitative research.
 - Data analysis techniques.**
 - Dissertation Concept Paper.
 - Delimitation of the test.

⁴ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 59.

⁵ Ibid., 48.

6. James Sampson expressed his opinion in the debate concerning the quantitative and the qualitative research methods, saying:⁶

- Qualitative and quantitative research methods can be appropriately integrated to make distinct and substantial contributions to knowledge.**
- The Philosophical assumption of qualitative and quantitative methods is incompatible, and using both methods is inappropriate.
- Qualitative research remains the only research method for doctorate students.
- Qualitative and quantitative research methods are complementary, and mixed-method designs are appropriate.

7. One element is essential in your dissertation component to avoid your research leading to inconsequential research findings.⁷

- Statement of Problems.
- Research Method Draft.
- Social Significances.
- Research Questions.**

⁶ Ibid., 7.

⁷ Ibid., 28.

8. The way in which the European Union operates is regulated by a series of Treaties and various other agreements having similar status. Together they constitute what is known as,⁸

- Primary legislation.**
- Acquis.*
- Secondary legislation.
- Legislative procedures.

9. What contains Acts of Accession in the European Union's primary legislation? ⁹

- The various legal acts adopted under the Treaties form the European Union's secondary legislation.
- The principles and regulations ratification.
- The technical details of transitional arrangements and secondary legislation requiring amendment.**
- An opportunity to become a party to a treaty already negotiated and signed by other states.

10. According to the general use, the term 'research' can be used in many ways. However, how does the Turabian Rule of Style use the term?¹⁰

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (European Commission, 2021), 72.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 76.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 19.

- Turabian uses research to answer questions and obtain information.
- Turabian uses research in a specific way, which means a process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that not only the researcher, but others want to solve.**
- Turabian described the research as a tool that helps students and researchers add much to their knowledge and ability to communicate it.
- Turabian described the research as creating new knowledge and using existing knowledge in a new and creative way to generate new concepts.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.